

A Compact Switched-Capacitor Multi-Bit Quantizer for Low-Power High-Resolution Delta-Sigma ADCs

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Abstract—This paper proposes a compact switched-capacitor (SC) multi-bit flash quantizer for low-power high-resolution delta-sigma modulators ($\Delta\Sigma$ s). First, a general power model for single-loop $\Delta\Sigma$ s is presented to show the importance of using multi-bit quantization when facing high-resolution specifications. In this context, a SC multi-bit quantizer circuit is proposed, which exhibits low-power operation, high modularity, single comparator design and compatibility with both multi-feedforward $\Delta\Sigma$ architectures and other SC low-power circuit techniques, like clocked comparators and switched OpAmps. A practical 50-kHz 16-bit $\Delta\Sigma$ design case is also presented.

I. INTRODUCTION

Portable smart sensing applications demand low-power high-resolution ADC circuits with a reduced bandwidth (typically below 1 MHz) but with dynamic range values exceeding 90 dB. Typically, $\Delta\Sigma$ modulators ($\Delta\Sigma$ s) are employed for these high-resolution data converters, as they relax the specifications for analog blocks at the expense of increasing signal oversampling ratios. However, their integration in modern CMOS technologies with increasing process variability and supply-voltage downscaling has become a real circuit design challenge. This fact can be noticed by the proportionally small number of circuit implementations above 15 ENOB reported in literature [1] compared to other areas of the ADC design space with similar figure-of-merit values.

A common choice to improve the dynamic range of single-loop $\Delta\Sigma$ s is the use of multi-bit quantization, as in the architecture example of Fig. 1(c). Compared to high-order noise shapers, which tend to introduce instability issues, or upscaled oversampling frequencies, with the corresponding increment of dynamic power consumption, the non-linearity associated with multi-bit quantization can be compensated in practice by digitally-assisted dynamic element matching (DEM) techniques at the feedback DAC. Classically, the signal summation and multi-bit quantization required in Fig. 1(c) is implemented separately at the cost of an active ladder and eventually a resistive-string for reference generation [2]. Alternatively, the use of capacitive summation based on passive charge sharing is an attractive solution because of its simplicity and low-power operation, although the corresponding signal attenuation may require pre-amplification or reference scaling [3]. Other trends in hybrid multi-bit $\Delta\Sigma$ s [4] replace the flash quantizer by another type of Nyquist-rate ADC, like pipeline, two-step flash, cyclic, tracking, integrating or synchronous/asynchronous successive-approximation register (SAR) [5]–[7]. In many cases, the overall ADC sensitivity and robustness against circuit non-idealities (e.g. latency) result

Figure 1. Comparative examples of high-resolution single-loop $\Delta\Sigma$ s: single-bit third-order (a), single-bit fourth-order (b) and 3-bit second-order architecture (c). Optimized coefficients obtained from [12].

impaired with respect to conventional $\Delta\Sigma$ s embedding flash quantizers. Finally, due to the supply voltage downscaling of modern CMOS technologies, it may be convenient to quantize signal amplitudes in the time/frequency domains, like the case of pulse width modulation (PWM) [8], time-encoding quantization [9], or more common voltage-to-frequency conversion by the means of voltage controlled oscillators (VCOs) [10], [11]. The latter also allows to increase the shaping order of the $\Delta\Sigma$ loop by simply using a phase detector instead of a frequency detector. Beside, they can be designed to automatically implement data weighted averaging (DWA) rotation on the thermometer code feeding the DAC. Unfortunately, the inherent non-linearity and process/temperature sensitivity of these schemes prevent their use in high-resolution ADCs.

This paper presents a compact switched-capacitor (SC) multi-bit flash quantizer topology for high-resolution $\Delta\Sigma$ s, which exhibits low-power operation, high modularity, single comparator design and compatibility with both multi-feedforward architectures and SC low-power circuit techniques, like clocked comparators and switched OpAmps [13].

II. $\Delta\Sigma$ MODULATOR POWER MODEL

Before introducing the new SC multi-bit quantizer circuit, this section presents a power consumption model for single-loop $\Delta\Sigma$ Ms to show the impact of architecture selection and illustrate the main trade-offs when optimizing for high resolution. For the benefit of generalization, circuit efficiency will be considered ideal, and only dynamic power consumption due to the signal processing itself will be evaluated.

In general, power consumption in a $\Delta\Sigma$ loop is dominated by the first integrator. Given a single-ended model clocked at f_s with integrating capacitor C_{i1} and supply voltage V_{DD} , the minimum dynamic power consumption due to the update of the state variable at the output of the first stage (ΔV_{out1}) is:

$$P_{\min} = \underbrace{C_{i1} |\Delta V_{out1}| f_s}_{I_{DD}} V_{DD} = \frac{C_{s1}}{a_1} \alpha_1 V_{DD}^2 \text{OSR} f_{\text{nyq}} \quad (1)$$

$$\alpha_1 \doteq \frac{|\Delta V_{out1}|}{V_{DD}},$$

where C_{s1} and a_1 are the sampling capacitor and integrator coefficient, respectively, OSR is the oversampling ratio, and the introduced parameter α_1 indicates the normalized dynamics at the output of the first stage, which can be determined through high-level simulations.

Under a given $\text{SNDR}_{\text{peak}}$ specification, and accounting for intrinsic modulator signal-to-quantization-noise ratio (SQNR), the following relations holds:

$$\text{SNDR}_{\text{peak}}^{-1} = \text{STNR}^{-1} + \text{SQNR}^{-1}, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{STNR} = \frac{A_{\text{peak}}^2}{2} \frac{C_{s1} \text{OSR}}{kT} = \frac{\alpha_{OL}^2 V_{DD}^2}{8} \frac{C_{s1} \text{OSR}}{kT}; \quad (3)$$

$$\alpha_{OL} \doteq \frac{2A_{\text{peak}}}{V_{DD}}, \quad (4)$$

where STNR is the signal-to-thermal-noise (kT/C) ratio of the $\Delta\Sigma$ modulator determined by the input peak amplitude A_{peak} , which in turn can be related to the theoretical available input full-scale (V_{DD}) through the attenuation coefficient α_{OL} here also defined. As usual, k stands for the Boltzmann constant and T is the absolute temperature. Now equations (2)-(4) can be rewritten in order to determine C_{s1} :

$$C_{s1} = \frac{8kT \text{SNDR}_{\text{peak}}}{\alpha_{OL}^2 V_{DD}^2 \text{OSR} (1 - \alpha_{QN})}; \quad \alpha_{QN} \doteq \frac{\text{SNDR}_{\text{peak}}}{\text{SQNR}} < 1. \quad (5)$$

Modulator architecture and parameters must be chosen in order to have a SQNR larger than the expected resolution, formally expressed by the inequality in (5). A closer look at the same equation will also reveal that α_{QN} is a function of OSR through SQNR, indicating two things: sampling capacitor does not scales proportionally to the inverse of OSR; once a specific architecture is chosen, a minimum OSR must be adopted in order to satisfy the inequality in (5). Finally, the expression for the minimum dynamic power consumption can be derived once (5) is substituted into (1):

$$P_{\min} = \text{SNDR}_{\text{peak}} f_{\text{nyq}} 8kT k_{\text{mod}}, \quad (6)$$

$$k_{\text{mod}} \doteq \frac{\alpha_1}{a_1 \alpha_{OL}^2 (1 - \alpha_{QN})}. \quad (7)$$

Basically, the above model lumps all the $\Delta\Sigma$ architecture details in the k_{mod} coefficient (i.e. internal dynamics, capacitor scaling, input full-scale loss and quantization noise margin), while on the other side only standard ADC performance ($\text{SNDR}_{\text{peak}}$ and f_{nyq}) and operative conditions (kT) are specified. In order to validate the above power model, four high-resolution $\Delta\Sigma$ design examples are evaluated with a common 50-kHz bandwidth and 16-bit $\text{SNDR}_{\text{peak}}$ specification at room temperature: the single-bit third-order $\Delta\Sigma$ architecture of Fig. 1(a) running at $\times 128$ oversampling ($L=3$, $\text{OSR}=128$, $N=1$) as a design reference; the still single-bit but fourth-order modulator of Fig. 1(b) operated at $\times 96$ Nyquist rate ($L=4$, $\text{OSR}=96$, $N=1$); the 3-bit second-order $\Delta\Sigma$ loop of Fig. 1(c) when overclocked at $\times 128$ ($L=2$, $\text{OSR}=128$, $N=3$); and the same multi-bit architecture but reducing its oversampling ratio down to $\times 96$ ($L=2$, $\text{OSR}=96$, $N=3$). Fig. 2 to 4 show the results obtained from their behavioral simulation, while Table I summarizes the extracted coefficients for the power model.

Figure 2. Output PSDs for the four $\Delta\Sigma$ design examples at -6dB_{FS} input.

Figure 3. SQNR curves and peak values for the four $\Delta\Sigma$ design examples.

Figure 4. Histograms of the first-integrator occupancy (V_{out1}) for the four $\Delta\Sigma M$ design examples. Note that these statistics do not apply for ΔV_{out1} .

Table I. POWER MODEL (7) FOR THE FOUR $\Delta\Sigma M$ DESIGN EXAMPLES.

Parameter	$L=3$	$L=4$	$L=2$	$L=2$
	OSR=128	OSR=96	OSR=128	OSR=96
α_1	0.1	0.2	1	1
α_1	0.0411	0.0859	0.0823	0.0821
α_{OL}	0.596	0.531	0.794	0.794
α_{QN}	0.449	0.206	0.120	0.246
k_{mod}	2.103	1.921	0.148	0.173

According to the proposed $\Delta\Sigma M$ power model, the combination of multi-bit quantization with low-order noise shaping and moderate oversampling ratios can save almost one order of magnitude on dynamic power consumption, regardless of the particular CMOS circuit realization. This prediction is consistent with the simulation results of Fig. 5. Hence, it is clear the interest of multi-bit quantizer circuits when optimizing the power efficiency of high-resolution $\Delta\Sigma M$ s.

Figure 5. Histograms and averages of the first-integrator dynamic power consumption for the four $\Delta\Sigma M$ design examples.

Figure 6. Half-circuit SC topology of the proposed multi-bit quantizer for the 9-level design case (a) and equivalent thresholds (b).

III. COMPACT SC MULTI-BIT QUANTIZER

Fig. 6(a) shows the half-circuit SC topology of the new multi-bit quantizer for the 9-level design case. The proposed scheme incorporates a ladder network of matched capacitors $C_{0...4}$ operated with non-overlapped clock phases $\phi_{1,2}$, where V_{FS} stands for the input full scale of the half circuit and $t_{3...0}$ is the generated thermal code. During ϕ_1 , all capacitors are reset. Once in ϕ_2 , C_0 samples the input signal V_{inp} to be quantized and charge redistribution occurs in the ladder so the proper voltages $V_{0...3}$ are established at the input of each comparator. For the purpose of implementing the quantization thresholds of Fig. 6(b), a specific capacitance ratio C_j/C_0 is required for each element $j=1...4$. Indeed, the design of the capacitive ladder network involves a linear system of n equations, being $1+2n$ the number of quantization levels. It can be shown that the general solution follows:

$$\frac{C_j}{C_0} = \begin{cases} \frac{4(j+n)^2 - 1}{4n(1+2n)} & j \in [1 \dots n-1] \\ \frac{1}{(1+2n) \left(1 - 4n \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{4(j+n)^2 - 1}\right)} & j = n \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

In the particular case of Fig. 6 ($n=4$), the exact matching ratios are $C_{1...4}/C_0 = \{\frac{11}{16}, \frac{143}{144}, \frac{65}{48}, \frac{5}{24}\}$. In practice, such ratios can be rounded according to the layout convenience thanks to the robustness against technology mismatching exhibited in Fig. 7. One advantage of the proposed quantizer is its compactness and modularity that translates into low-power operation. Also, since all comparators of Fig. 6 latch at the same voltage threshold, a single CMOS circuit design can be reused. Furthermore, the proposed quantizer is compatible not only with other low-power SC techniques, like clocked comparators and switched OpAmps, but also with multiple-feedforward $\Delta\Sigma M$ architectures, as shown in the design example of next section. In terms of signal attenuation, the maximum loss caused by the passive network of Fig. 6(a) corresponds to V_{n-1} and equals $\frac{2n-1}{4n-1}$, which is around 6 dB. Finally, the effect of parasitic capacitance at the input of each comparator should be in principle neglectable according to the results of Fig. 8.

Figure 7. SQNR curves and peak values for the $\Delta\Sigma M$ design example of Fig. 1(c) when using the proposed multi-bit quantizer of Fig. 6 as a function of the capacitance matching granularity in (8).

Figure 8. SQNR curves for the $\Delta\Sigma M$ design example of Fig. 1(c) when using the proposed multi-bit quantizer of Fig. 6 as a function of the comparator parasitic capacitance normalized to the quantizer sampling capacitor C_0 .

IV. DESIGN EXAMPLE

In order to demonstrate the capabilities of the proposed multi-bit quantizer for high-resolution $\Delta\Sigma M$ s, the 9-level circuit design example of Fig. 6 have been applied to the second-order architecture of Fig. 1(c) to achieve a target bandwidth and dynamic range of 50 kHz and 16 bit, respectively. The equivalent SC schematic is shown in Fig. 9 with $2\cdot V_{pp}$ differential full scale ($V_{io}=0.4V$ and $V_{hi}=1.4V$ at 1.8-V supply) and 12.8-MHz sampling rate ($OSR=128$). In this case, switched OpAmps are also employed at the noise shaper to save power consumption, while bubble error correction (BEC) and DEM assisted techniques are used at the quantizer and the feedback DAC, respectively. The exact capacitance ratios from (8) have been simplified to $C_{1...4}/C_0 = \{\frac{11}{16}, \frac{143}{144}, \frac{65}{48}, \frac{5}{24}\} \approx \{\frac{3}{4}, \frac{4}{4}, \frac{5}{4}, \frac{1}{4}\}$

Figure 9. Simplified schematic of a 9-level second-order SC $\Delta\Sigma M$ circuit using the proposed multi-bit quantizer of Fig. 6.

Figure 10. Output PSDs for the 9-level second-order SC $\Delta\Sigma M$ circuit of Fig. 9 obtained from behavioral and electrical simulation at $-1dB_{FS}$ input.

with unitary capacitance $C_u=0.5pF$. In this sense, the $4\cdot C_u$ multiplicity of C_0 is also exploited in Fig. 9 to implement the weights of the nested feedforward paths of Fig. 1(c). The $\Delta\Sigma M$ results obtained in Fig. 10 return good SQNR matching between behavioral and electrical simulations.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A power model for single-loop $\Delta\Sigma M$ s has been presented to show the importance of using multi-bit quantization when facing high-resolution ADC specifications. In this context, a compact SC multi-bit flash quantizer topology has been proposed, which exhibits low-power operation, high modularity, single comparator design and compatibility with both multi-feedforward $\Delta\Sigma M$ architectures and SC low-power circuit techniques, like clocked comparators and switched OpAmps. A practical 50-kHz 16-bit $\Delta\Sigma M$ design case has been presented to demonstrate the capabilities of the proposed multi-bit quantizer circuit. This work has been partially funded by European Commission H2020-FETPROACT-2016-732032 and supported by TecnioSpring+ TECSPR16-1-0056.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Murmann, "ADC Performance Survey 1997-2017," available online: <http://www.stanford.edu/~murmann/adcsurvey.html>.
- [2] J. Xu, M. K. Islam, S. Wang, and Z. Yang, "A $13\mu\text{W}$ 87dB Dynamic Range Implantable $\Delta\Sigma$ Modulator for Full-Spectrum Neural Recording," in *Proceedings of the 35th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society*, Jul 2013, pp. 2764–2767.
- [3] R. Gaggl, M. Inversi, and A. Wiesbauer, "A Power Optimized 14-bit SC $\Delta\Sigma$ Modulator for ADSL CO Applications," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference*, vol. 1, Feb 2004, pp. 82–514.
- [4] J. M. de la Rosa, R. Schreier, K. P. Pun, and S. Pavan, "Next-Generation Delta-Sigma Converters: Trends and Perspectives," *IEEE Journal on Emerging and Selected Topics in Circuits and Systems*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 484–499, Dec 2015.
- [5] S. Porrazzo, A. Morgado, D. S. S. Bello, F. Cannillo, C. V. Hoof, R. F. Yazicioglu, A. H. M. van Roermund, and E. Cantatore, "A $155\text{-}\mu\text{W}$ 88-dB DR Discrete-Time $\Delta\Sigma$ Modulator for Digital Hearing Aids Exploiting a Summing SAR ADC Quantizer," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Circuits and Systems*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 573–582, Oct 2013.
- [6] M. Ranjbar, A. Mehrabi, O. Oliaei, and F. Carrez, "A 3.1 mW Continuous-Time $\Delta\Sigma$ Modulator with 5-bit Successive Approximation Quantizer for WCDMA," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 45, no. 8, pp. 1479–1491, Aug 2010.
- [7] T. C. Wang, Y. H. Lin, and C. C. Liu, "A 0.022 mm^2 98.5 dB SNDR Hybrid Audio $\Delta\Sigma$ Modulator with Digital ELD Compensation in 28-nm CMOS," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 50, no. 11, pp. 2655–2664, Nov 2015.
- [8] N. Maghari and U. K. Moon, "A Third-Order DT $\Delta\Sigma$ Modulator Using Noise-Shaped Bi-Directional Single-Slope Quantizer," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 46, no. 12, pp. 2882–2891, Dec 2011.
- [9] E. Prefasi, L. Hernandez, S. Paton, A. Wiesbauer, R. Gaggl, and E. Pun, "A 0.1 mm^2 , Wide Bandwidth Continuous-Time $\Sigma\Delta$ ADC Based on a Time Encoding Quantizer in $0.13\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ CMOS," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 44, no. 10, pp. 2745–2754, Oct 2009.
- [10] A. Iwata, N. Sakimura, M. Nagata, and T. Morie, "The Architecture of Delta Sigma Analog-to-Digital Converters Using a Voltage-Controlled Oscillator as a Multibit Quantizer," *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. II*, vol. 46, no. 7, pp. 941–945, Jul 1999.
- [11] M. Z. Straayer and M. H. Perrott, "A 12-Bit, 10-MHz Bandwidth, Continuous-Time $\Sigma\Delta$ ADC With a 5-Bit, 950-MS/s VCO-Based Quantizer," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 43, no. 4, pp. 805–814, April 2008.
- [12] L. Yao, M. Steyaert, and W. Sansen, *Low-Power Low-Voltage Sigma-Delta Modulators in Nanometer CMOS*. Springer, 2006.
- [13] J. Crols and M. Steyaert, "Switched-OpAmp: An Approach to Realize Full CMOS Switched-Capacitor Circuits at Very Low Power Supply Voltages," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 29, no. 8, pp. 936–942, Aug 1994.